

TECHNOLOGY OF IMPROVING THE LEARNING AND COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILDREN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11122545>

Abstract. *To activate the cognitive activity of junior schoolchildren at the lessons of Russian language can be creative approach of teachers to the preparation and conduct of lessons, the use of new non-standard forms, methods of work and technology, in this regard, this article reveals ways to improve the learning and cognitive activity of junior schoolchildren.*

Keywords: *cognitive activity, elementary school, motive, game technologies, knowledge, skills, skills and competence.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern education there is a problem of choice of teaching methods, but not all methods are effective in activating the learning and cognitive activity of students. At the moment, based on modern educational practice, most students have a low level of cognitive interest in the subject, more and more often there are children with an active unwillingness to learn.

Junior school age is a very important period in the formation of a child's personality, the development of his thinking processes and the formation of cognitive activity, the ability to learn. That is why a modern teacher, at school should constantly stimulate and support the student's interest in learning subjects, their curiosity to learn something new.

One of the urgent problems worrying teachers is the question of how to develop a child's sustained interest in learning, knowledge and the need for their independent search. The solution of these problems relies on the motivational sphere of the child. Elementary school students cannot learn "for themselves". Sometimes they learn for a grade, sometimes for praise, sometimes for gifts. But any of these motives comes to an end. Therefore, teachers need to form learning motivation on the basis of cognitive interest. The child should like his activity, and it should be available to him. It is not interesting to do the same thing from lesson to lesson. But if pupils at each lesson have an opportunity to solve problems they can solve independently, it will attract interest in their activity. Solving this or that problem situation at the lesson contributes to the activation of their learning and cognitive activity, as well as the formation of the desire to learn.

Problematic learning situation allows solving the tasks of learning activity, in which the pupil as a subject of activity is organically included. Activity of work is a contradiction between the urgent need to introduce productive creative teaching methods and insufficient not developed methodology of their use in elementary school.

Numerous uses show that the formation of a full-fledged positive learning activity requires purposeful work, where the main place is occupied by the game, the purpose of which is the active mastering of the curriculum. When children are included in a game situation, their interest in learning activities is noticeably increased and their performance is enhanced.

Lessons, which are taught with the use of technologies of visual and entertaining character, fascinate students with their unusual conduct, bring joy, which contributes to the creation of students emotional mood for the entire lesson, causes a positive attitude to the work performed, also improves the overall performance, broaden outlook, develop vision, observation, attentiveness, as well as wit.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The problem of improving learning and cognitive activity in various aspects was considered by teachers: F. I. Buslaev, G. I. Shchukina. Also the concept of "cognitive activity" is considered in the works of V.S. Ilyin, E.I. Krasnovsky, G.I. Shchukina.

The problem and methods of formation of cognitive processes are devoted to the studies of A. I. Herzen, O. P. Rozhkov, A. N. Shobonova, as well as M. A. Puilova, I. Terskikh. A., Naleskaya S. L. In the formation of cognitive interests researchers give the central place to learning, identify the types of its stimulation: the content of educational material, organization of cognitive activity, interaction between the participants of the cognitive process.

The issue of development of cognitive interest of junior schoolchildren in learning activities is reflected in the works of Khaitova N.F., U. Begimkulov, A.A. Abdukodirov, M. Lutfullaev, as well as Panin, T.S., Stone M.E., Shchukin, R.I.[14]

However, in pedagogical science the topic of development of cognitive interest of junior schoolchildren in Russian language in junior classes finds weak coverage, which determined the relevance of the study.

Cognitive activity is one of the main forms of child's activity, which stimulates learning activity, on the basis of cognitive interest. Therefore, the improvement of cognitive activity of schoolchildren is an integral part of the improvement of teaching methods. Analysis of the concepts of schoolchildren's activity in the learning process involves the study of such pedagogical laws as the emergence of the need to learn, the creation of a positive emotional atmosphere of learning, contributing to the optimal tension of mental and strength of students.

The idea of intensifying learning has a long history. Since ancient times it has been known that mental activity contributes to better memorization, deeper penetration into the essence of subjects, processes and phenomena. The desire to stimulate intellectual activity is based on certain philosophical views. Posing problem questions to the interlocutor and his difficulties in finding answers to them were characteristic of Socrates' discussions, the same technique was known in the school of Pythagoras.

The Russian methodologist A.Y. Gerd, who formulated important provisions of developmental learning, achieved great success in the search for new lively teaching methods. He quite fully expressed the essence of the process of independent mastering of new knowledge, arguing that if the student himself observes and compares, then "his knowledge is clearer, more definite and constitute his property, acquired by himself and therefore valuable".

The actual problem determining the essence of personality formation is activity, its place in social life, its influence on the development of new generations.

According to D.B. Elkonin, learning activity is an activity that has as its content the mastering of generalized ways of action in the sphere of scientific concepts. Such activity should be stimulated by adequate motives. If it is possible to form such motives in students, then, thanks to this, those general motives of activity are supported and filled with new content, which are associated with the position of the schoolboy, with the implementation of socially significant and evaluated activity[13].

According to I.A. Zimnya, learning activity is the subject's activity of mastering generalized ways of learning actions and self-development in the process of solving learning tasks set by the teacher, on the basis of external control and evaluation, passing into self-control and self-assessment.

OBSERVATION

Educational and cognitive activity, equips knowledge, skills, abilities, skills; contributes to the education of worldview, moral, aesthetic qualities of students; develops their cognitive powers, personal education, activity, independence, cognitive interest; opens and realizes the potential capabilities of students; introduces to the search and creative activity. The basis of active learning and cognitive activity is determined by the components: interest in learning; initiative; cognitive activity. The noted features of activation of learning activity of junior classes allow us to indicate its main directions, taking into account the special role of interest.

In the organization of active learning activity of junior schoolchildren it is advisable to single out the corresponding direction as an independent one. Other directions are defined as conditions of realization of several components of active learning activity of pupils.

The ability to learn is the ability to independently solve a learning task, to achieve the set goal at the lesson, but it is impossible without a consciously acceptance and creative fulfillment of learning activity with obligatory reflection of activity, self-analysis and self-assessment of the degree of success of their own actions.

Based on the considered concepts of "learning activity" we can conclude that learning activity is a purposeful activity, which is aimed at solving the learning task and acquiring knowledge and experience. As it was already mentioned above, the concept of "learning and cognitive activity" is a combination of cognitive and learning activities. Cognitive activity is a conscious interaction with the surrounding world using mental processes, and learning activity is conditioned as a purposeful activity, which is aimed at solving the learning task and acquiring knowledge and experience. Given the above, learning and cognitive activity is a conscious, purposeful activity aimed at gaining experience, solving learning problems and the development of personality as a whole.

Program material on the Russian language in the primary grades provides an opportunity to conduct a very large number of lessons using non-standard forms, methods and technologies, as a creatively working teacher discovers for himself and his students more and more new constructions.

We can highlight the most frequently used in elementary school in Russian language lessons: game technology, creative tasks, logical tasks, speech warm-ups, creating problem situations. In the process of learning to use game technology allows you to meet the need to communicate, work in a team, in addition, develops mental abilities. In recent years there are new game technologies: story - role-playing game, game "**What? Where? When?**", "**Brain Ring**", games-tasks, games-competitions, contest of fairy tales, game "**Finish the word**", "**Collect words**" and others.

The task of games is that children learn independently, working together and actively helping each other, also activates the desire of children to contact with each other, eliminates the barrier between teacher and student. Younger pupils are very pleased to perform creative tasks with verbal creativity (staging scenes, story - composition) - this contributes to the transfer of their own opinion, as the content goes beyond the studied, and the theme of the story requires reflection. The value of such technologies lies in the fact that when performing them, cognitive and thinking activity is activated, as the tasks cannot be solved "from the get-go", thus forcing the pupil to reflect, think, assume, make inferences.

RESULTS

To improve learning and cognitive activity and increase interest in learning is necessary at every stage of the lesson, masterfully using various methods and techniques of work. When using them significantly increases the cognitive interest of junior schoolchildren to the Russian language, the lesson becomes more rich, bright, unusual, emotional, activates the learning and cognitive activity of junior schoolchildren. Forms and methods of work at the lessons of Russian language can be very diverse. Everything depends on the creativity and professionalism of the teacher.

Using a variety of forms and techniques in the learning process, the teacher must take into account the individual characteristics of students, their attitude to the subject, the degree of difficulty of questions and tasks.

The solution of this or that problem at the lesson contributes to the formation of the motive of activity, students, the activation of their cognitive activity. The course of Russian language in elementary school contains a very large amount of knowledge from orthography, morphology and syntax. All this is not only necessary to give children in a theoretical form, but also to work out grammatical skills.

You can give all the material in a ready-made form: introduce the rules, give examples, but you can go the other way: give students the opportunity to see the pattern. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to teach children to understand the purpose of the task and the results they have achieved.

The above suggested technologies promote children's interest, awaken their interest in the subject, improve and enrich the speech of junior schoolchildren. In addition, it should be emphasized that the educational material presented in a game form, more steadily assimilated by students, allows you to learn the language with great pleasure, not getting tired of the abundance of tasks and information. And thus are a productive means of improving the learning and cognitive activity of junior schoolchildren in Russian language lessons.

CONCLUSION

Lesson is a living cell of educational process. Everything that is most important and most important for a student is accomplished in the classroom. 45 minutes is a slice of life for teachers and students, which can be lived brightly, emotionally and become memorable and on the contrary, it can be boring and uninteresting.

Improvement of teaching process is determined by teachers' aspiration to activate learning and cognitive activity of students. The essence of the activation of learning of junior schoolchildren is in such an organization of learning activities, in which the student gains basic skills of knowledge acquisition and on this basis learn to independently "extract knowledge".

To activate learning and cognitive activity, it is necessary to interest the child, to motivate. To form a full-fledged positive learning motivation requires purposeful work, where one of the important places is occupied by the game, the purpose of which is the active mastering of learning activity, learning task. When children are included in a game situation, their interest in learning activities increases noticeably, and their efficiency increases.

The main components of the improvement of learning and cognitive activity will be:

- achievements of the child in learning activities;
- recognition by the team;
- level of independence of the pupil;
- the formation of sustainable motivation to study subjects;
- the presence of a creative approach when performing various tasks;
- increasing the level of mastering the material;
- forming the need for learning;
- display of curiosity;
- the ability to apply their knowledge in practical activities;
- experiencing by the pupil the joy of achievement;
- Ability to defend their point of view;
- active and successful participation in Olympiads, competitions, intellectual games.

The elementary school teacher has a great responsibility to properly organize the learning and cognitive activities of students so that they can succeed in their studies.

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